

Endocrine Influences on Mental Health: Hormone Therapy and Surgical Outcomes in Transgender Patients

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ABSTRACT

This review article explores the intersection of transgender medicine and mental health, focusing on various mental health outcomes associated with different treatment and social conditions. The aim is to provide a comprehensive analysis of how hormone therapy, gender-affirming surgery, lack of treatment, socioeconomic factors and support impact the mental well-being of transgender individuals. By synthesizing current research, this article seeks to inform healthcare professionals about the nuances of mental health in transgender patients and highlight areas for further study and improvement in care.

Keywords: Transgender; Mental health; Social Conditions

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Difficulties in Psychological Health:

Transgender individuals often face unique challenges regarding their mental health, largely influenced by their medical and social circumstances. Disparities in mental health outcomes are observed across different treatment modalities and socioeconomic backgrounds. For instance, transgender people frequently experience higher rates of depression, anxiety, and suicidal ideation compared to the general population. These mental health issues are often exacerbated by experiences of stigma, discrimination, and social rejection. The lack of acceptance in various social settings, including workplaces, schools, and even within families, contributes significantly to the psychological distress experienced by many transgender individuals.

To fully appreciate these challenges, it's important to understand the historical context and the evolution of gender dysphoria as a medical diagnosis. Initially, terms like "transvestism" were used to describe what we now recognize as transgender identities. Pioneers like Magnus Hirschfeld distinguished between sexual orientation and gender identity, paving the way for more nuanced understandings. In the mid-20th century, Harry Benjamin introduced the term "transsexual," which later evolved into "transgender" in the 1970s.^[1] These changes in terminology reflect a broader shift from viewing transgender identities as pathological to understanding them as variations of human diversity.

A significant milestone in this evolution was the inclusion of gender dysphoria as an official psychiatric diagnosis in the fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders in 2013, replacing the older term "gender identity disorder."^[1] This change aimed to reduce stigma and recognize that the distress experienced by transgender individuals is often due to societal rejection rather than the identity itself. Further progress was made with the introduction of the term "gender incongruence" in the International Classification of Diseases in 2019, categorizing it under conditions related to sexual health rather than mental health.^[1] This reclassification further reduced the pathologization of transgender identities (Figure 1).

1. Gender as a diagnostic category in DSM and ICD

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Diagnostic classification and year	Diagnostic terms	Comments
DSM-II 1968	No diagnostic category for gender incongruence	'Transvestitism' is included in the sexual deviations
DSM-III 1980	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transsexualism, with subclassification as asexual, homosexual, or heterosexual, and with reference to the sex assigned at birth. • Gender Identity Disorder of Childhood (GIDC) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transvestism is a differential diagnosis • GIDs are in the section on Psychosexual Disorders, together with Paraphilias, Psychosexual Dysfunctions, and Ego-dystonic Homosexuality
DSM-III-R 1987	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender Identity Disorder of Childhood • Transsexualism • Gender Identity Disorder of Adolescence or Adulthood, Nontranssexual Type (GIDAANT) 	GIDAANT: for cross-gender identified individuals who did not pursue reassignment.
ICD-10 1990	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transsexualism, duration ≥ 2 years • Dual-role transvestism • Gender identity disorder of childhood (no specific duration requirement) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fetishistic transvestism is a diagnostic category in the 'Disorders of sexual preference.'
DSM-IV(-TR) 1994 (2000)	Gender Identity Disorder. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children are coded differently than Adolescents or Adults. • Specify if sexually attracted to males, females, both, or neither 	GIDs are included in the section on Sexual and Gender Identity Disorders, which also contains Sexual Dysfunctions and Paraphilias.
DSM-5 2013	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender Dysphoria in Adolescents and Adults • Gender Dysphoria in Children. • A minimal duration of 6 months is required for both diagnoses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GD is placed in a distinct section. The terms Gender and Sex are defined and used differently. • Contrary to DSM-IV, sexual orientation is not specified.
ICD-11 2019-2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender Incongruence of adolescence or adulthood. several months. • Gender Incongruence of Childhood. In children, the incongruence must have persisted for about 2 years. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Included in the chapter on 'Conditions related to sexual health' • ICD-11's primary focus is experience of incongruence between experienced gender and assigned sex; In ICD-11, distress and functional impairment are described as common associated features, particularly in disapproving social environments, but are not required; in contrast, DSM-5 requires clinically significant distress or impairment for diagnosis. • Body Integrity Dysphoria is a differential diagnosis

Incidence and Prevalence:

Understanding the incidence and prevalence of transgender and gender diverse (TGD) individuals is crucial for addressing their healthcare needs. Epidemiological data indicates that the proportion of TGD people varies

significantly depending on the definitions and methods used. A systematic review of recent studies, which included data from large healthcare systems and population surveys, found that the estimated prevalence of TGD individuals ranges from 0.3% to 0.5% among adults when a narrow definition of 'transgender' is used, and from 1.2% to 2.7% among children and adolescents. When broader definitions of gender diversity are applied, these proportions increase to 0.5-4.5% among adults (Figure 2) and 2.5-8.4% among children and adolescents (Figure 3).^[2] In recent years, there has been an upward trend in the number of people identifying as TGD. This increase in visibility highlights the growing recognition of gender diversity and emphasizes the need for inclusive and comprehensive healthcare policies and practices.

2. Number and population proportion of adults who self-reported transgender identity or gender diversity.

- Source: Reprinted from "Epidemiological considerations in transgender health: A systematic review with focus on higher quality data," by Zhang Q, Goodman M, Adams N, et al., 2020, *International Journal of Transgender Health*, 21(2), p. 125-137.
 - Not CC approved

Survey location, time period, age (Reference)	Case definition	Source of numerator	Numerator		Size of denominator	Percentage	
			Total	RFAB		Total	RFAB
Stockholm County, Sweden, 2014, ≥22 years (Ahs et al., 2018)	Desire to undergo treatment Feeling as person of different sex	Stockholm Public Health Cohort (SPHC) study questionnaire	121	61	50,157; 21,986 males and 28,571 females	0.5%	0.4%
Massachusetts, US, 2007-2009, 18-64 years (Corron et al., 2012)	Self-identity as transgender	Massachusetts Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance Survey (BRFSS) 2007-2009	779	561	28,176	2.8%	3.5%
Nationwide, US, 2014, ≥18 years (Crisman et al., 2017)	Self-identity as transgender	Annual cross-sectional telephone survey in all US states and 3 territories	807	NA	151,456 (62,086 cisgender males, 88,679 cisgender females)	0.5%	NA
Nationwide, Netherlands, 2013, 15-70 years (Kuyper & Wilsen, 2014) [†]	Incongruent gender identity Ambivalent gender identity	Sexual Health Survey	77**	32**	8,064 total (4052 males, 4012 females)	1.0%	0.8%
Taiwan University, Taiwan 2003-2004, first-year college students (Lai et al., 2010)	Self-reported gender dysphoria	Adult Self-Report Inventory-4, DSM-IV referenced rating	225	176	5010 total (2585 males, 2425 females)	4.5%	7.3%
Nationwide, US, 2010, 23-28 years (Reisner, Conon, et al., 2014)	Self-identity as transgender	Growing Up Today Study (GUTS)	26	16	7,881 (2,605 males and 5,226 females)	0.3%	0.3%
Flanders, Belgium, 14-80 years, 2011-2012 (Van Caenegem et al., 2015) [†]	Incongruent gender identity Ambivalent gender identity	Sexual Health Survey	11**	6**	1,799 (894 males, 905 females)	0.6%	0.6%
San Francisco, US, 18-71 years, 2013 (Tate et al., 2013)	One question about gender (Study 1) Two questions about sex recorded at birth and gender identity (Studies 2 and 3)	San Francisco State University, Department of Psychology Survey	37**	20**	Study 1: 238 Study 2: 364 (259 cisgender females, 99 cisgender males)	Study 1: 0.8% Study 2: 1.6%	Study 1: 1.9% Study 2: 0.8%
			Study 2: 6 (2 transgender, 4 non-binary)	Study 2: 2 transmen	Study 3: 388 (192 cisgender females, 184 cisgender males)	Study 3: 3.1%	Study 3: 1.6 [†]

[†]Includes a small proportion of adolescents, but the reported data do not allow evaluating results by age.

**Calculated based on reported percentages and denominator sizes.

† Results exclude non-binary participants whose sex recorded at birth is not known.

NA = Not available.

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- **Number and population proportion of children and adolescents with self- or parent-reported transgender identity and gender diversity**
 - Source: Reprinted from "Epidemiological considerations in transgender health: A systematic review with focus on higher quality data," by Zhang Q, Goodman M, Adams N, et al., 2020, *International Journal of Transgender Health*, 21(2), p. 125-137.

Survey location; time period, age (Reference)	Case definition	Source of numerator	Numerator			Size of denominator	Percentage		
			Total	AMAB	AFAB		Total	AMAB	AFAB
Boston, Massachusetts, US, 2006, 13-19 years (Almeida et al., 2009)	Self-identity as transgender	Boston Youth Survey data	17	11	6	1032	1.6%	NA	NA
Nationwide, New Zealand, 2012, secondary school students; age range not provided; 65% reported to be ≤15 years of age (Clark et al., 2014)	Self-identity as transgender	National survey of secondary school students	96	44	52	8164 (3669 males, 4495 females)	1.2%	1.2%	1.2%
	Not sure of gender identity		201	82	120		2.5%	2.2%	2.7%
Minnesota, USA, 2016, 9 th and 11 th grade (Eisenberg et al., 2017)	Self-identity as transgender	Minnesota Student Survey	2,198	NA	NA	80,929	2.7%	1.7%	3.6%
San Francisco, US, 2011, 11-13 years (Shields et al., 2013)	Self-identity as transgender	Youth Risk Behavior Survey at administered in middle schools	33	NA	NA	2701	1.3%	NA	NA
Zuid-Holland province, Netherlands, 1983, 4-11 years (Steensma et al., 2013)	Parent/primary caregiver report on gender variance	Baseline assessment in a longitudinal study of changes in sexual orientation and gender variant behavior	51	10	41	879 (406 males, 473 females)	5.8%	2.5%	8.7%
Florida and California, US, 2015, 9-12 th grade (Lowry et al., 2018)	High gender nonconformity based on a 7-point scale	Youth Risk Behavior Surveillance System	511*	408*	117*	6082 (2919 females, 3139 males)**	8.4%	13.0%	4.0%

*Calculated based on reported percentages and denominator sizes.

**Numbers of male and female participants reported in the article do not add up to total.

NA = Not available.

Scope of review:

This review aims to analyze these disparities by examining the mental health levels of transgender patients undergoing hormone therapy (HT), gender-affirming surgery, receiving no treatment, those from varying socioeconomic backgrounds and those with family support. Understanding these differences is crucial for developing tailored interventions and improving the overall well-being of transgender individuals.

To ensure the thoroughness and accuracy of our review, we employed a rigorous and systematic search strategy across several key databases, including PubMed, Google Scholar, and Scopus. Our search included terms such as “transgender mental health,” “hormone therapy outcomes,” “gender-affirming surgery,” “family support for transgender individuals,” and “socioeconomic factors in transgender health.” We targeted literature from the past decade to ensure the inclusion of the most current research, while also integrating seminal works that provide essential historical insights. No language restrictions were applied, allowing for a diverse and comprehensive collection of studies. In addition to peer-reviewed articles, we examined conference proceedings and relevant unpublished materials to ensure a well-rounded perspective was shared. This meticulous approach aims to provide a detailed and reliable synthesis of the current knowledge on the mental health outcomes of transgender individuals under various treatment and social conditions.

REVIEW

Hormone Therapy and Mental Health Outcomes:

HT is a common treatment for transgender individuals seeking to align their physical appearance with their gender identity. Multiple studies indicate that HT can significantly improve mental health outcomes, reducing symptoms of depression, anxiety, and overall psychological distress. For instance, a study by Colizzi et al. reported that the proportion of transgender individuals with symptoms of depression decreased from 42% to 22% over 12 months of treatment.^[3] Additionally, Fisher et al. found that Beck Depression Inventory scores among transgender men decreased from a mean of 15.7 ± 12.3 to 8.1 ± 6.2 after six months of HT, representing a significant improvement ($P < 0.001$).^[4] Pelusi et al. also noted an increase in life satisfaction scores from 2.8 to 8.5 on a 10-point scale among transgender men after one year of testosterone treatment.^[5]

However, access to HT can be limited by various factors, including socioeconomic status and healthcare availability, which can impact the mental health benefits experienced by patients. Furthermore, despite these positive outcomes, it is worth noting that the results should be interpreted with caution, as the strength of evidence in these studies is low due to high risks of bias, small sample sizes, and potential confounding factors such as concurrent gender-affirming surgeries.

Significant findings have also been reported regarding the mental health outcomes of transgender youth undergoing gender-affirming HT. A recent study revealed a large reduction in body dissatisfaction and modest improvements in mental health over the first year of treatment. Specifically, participants experienced an average decrease in body dissatisfaction scores from 69.9 to 51.7, and depressive symptoms decreased from 9.4 to 7.3 (self-reported) and from 5.8 to 5.9 (clinician-reported). Anxiety symptoms also showed improvement, with significant reductions in total anxiety, panic, and school avoidance symptoms.^[6] These results showcase the critical role of HT in enhancing the mental well-being of transgender youth.

While the aforementioned studies all showcase a positive perspective, another interesting study cautioned about a potential downside of HT. It examined the associations between HT use and psychological well-being in perimenopausal and postmenopausal women. Researchers found that current HT use was linked to a higher likelihood of psychiatric diagnoses in the previous 12 months. Specifically, HT use was associated with self-reported diagnoses of depression, major depressive disorder, anxiety disorder, and symptoms such as nervousness, frightening thoughts, nightmares, and headaches. However, no differences emerged between different routes of administration or types of HT.^[7] The findings suggest that women using HT during the menopausal transition may experience worse psychological well-being and mental health compared to those not using HT, highlighting the importance of identifying and providing psychiatric support to women during this period.

Gender-Affirming Surgery and Mental Health Outcomes:

Gender-affirming surgery is another critical component of transgender healthcare. Research demonstrates that individuals who undergo gender-affirming surgery often experience substantial improvements in mental health.

For example, an investigation into the mental health benefits of gender-affirming surgeries among TGD people analyzed data from the 2015 US Transgender Survey with 27,715 participants. The study found that TGD individuals who had undergone gender-affirming surgery had significantly lower odds of past-month psychological distress (adjusted odds ratio [aOR], 0.58; 95% CI, 0.50-0.67), past-year smoking (aOR, 0.65; 95% CI, 0.57-0.75), and past-year suicidal ideation (aOR, 0.56; 95% CI, 0.50-0.64) compared to those who desired but had not yet received surgery.^[8] These findings underscore the importance of gender-affirming surgeries in improving mental health outcomes for TGD individuals, suggesting a critical need for policies that facilitate access to these surgeries.

Furthermore, another study which also used data from the 2015 U.S. Transgender Survey, highlighted a 42% decrease in psychological distress and a 44% decrease in suicidal ideation within a year after surgery among 3,559 transgender individuals who underwent gender-affirming surgery.^[9] This study highlights the importance of accessible gender-affirming care, demonstrating that such procedures can markedly improve mental health outcomes.

A study presented by the University of Virginia Health System investigated the impact of gender-affirming surgery on mental health and substance abuse in patients with gender dysphoria. Using a national insurance claims-based database, they compared patients who underwent gender-affirming surgery to those who did not, matched by comorbidities, age, and listed sex. The results demonstrated significant mental health improvements in the surgery group, with a decrease of 8.8% in the use of SSRIs or SNRIs, and reductions in postoperative depression (7.7%), anxiety (1.6%), suicidal ideation (5.2%), and suicide attempts (2.3%). Additionally, there were decreases in alcohol abuse (2.1%) and drug abuse (1.9%).^[10] These findings suggest that gender-affirming surgery not only reduces antidepressant use, but also significantly improves overall mental health outcomes in appropriately selected patients with gender dysphoria.

Despite these positive outcomes, barriers to accessing surgery, such as cost and availability, remain significant issues that can affect mental health outcomes. Many transgender individuals face substantial financial challenges in obtaining gender-affirming surgeries, as these procedures are often not covered by insurance or come with high out-of-pocket costs. Additionally, the availability of skilled surgeons and healthcare providers who specialize in gender-affirming surgeries is limited, particularly in rural or underserved areas. These barriers can lead to prolonged periods of gender dysphoria, increased psychological distress, and a higher incidence of mental health issues. Furthermore, the stigma and discrimination associated with seeking gender-affirming care can exacerbate these challenges, making it even more difficult for individuals in need to access the necessary medical interventions. Addressing these barriers through policy changes, improved insurance coverage, and increased availability of specialized healthcare services is crucial for enhancing the mental well-being of TGD populations.

No Treatment and Mental Health Outcomes:

Transgender individuals who do not receive any medical treatment, such as HT, often face the most severe mental health challenges. For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic the deferral of gender-affirming treatment highlighted the significant mental health risks associated with lack of care. The postponement of essential treatments increased distress and suicidality among transgender and gender non-conforming individuals.^[11] Without proper endocrine therapies and psychological support, transgender individuals are at greater risk of experiencing severe mental health issues, including heightened stress, anxiety, depression, and suicidal thoughts.

Socioeconomic Factors and Mental Health Outcomes:

Socioeconomic status also plays a crucial role in the mental health of transgender individuals. Those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds often face increased barriers to accessing healthcare, including HT and surgery, which can negatively impact their mental health. Research by Glintborg et al. suggests that transgender individuals in Denmark have a significantly higher risk of low socioeconomic status compared to their cisgender counterparts. The study found that transgender individuals were 5.6 times more likely to have low personal income and 4.4 times more likely to be unemployed or on welfare compared to controls.^[12] These socioeconomic disparities can lead to increased distress and lack of access to an endocrinologist, emphasizing the need for interventions to improve access to healthcare and support services for transgender individuals.

Additionally, another study examining the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on transgender and nonbinary individuals revealed that these populations faced exacerbated mental health challenges due to economic instability and reduced access to gender-affirming care. The research highlighted that structural vulnerabilities, such as economic, food, and housing insecurity, significantly contributed to worsening mental health outcomes, including increased levels of depression and anxiety. Specifically, the study found that 50.4% of the sample screened positive for depression and 45.8% for anxiety. Furthermore, 77% expected a reduction in their income, and 17% anticipated losing their health insurance.^[13] These socioeconomic disparities were strongly associated with increased psychological distress and suicidal ideation during the pandemic.

Family Support and Mental Health Outcomes:

Family support plays a crucial role in the mental health outcomes of transgender individuals. Acceptance and support from family members can significantly mitigate the psychological distress often experienced by transgender people. Transgender individuals who receive strong familial support report lower levels of depression, anxiety, and suicidal ideation compared to those who face rejection or lack of support from their families. Research has found that parental support is significantly associated with higher life satisfaction, lower perceived burden of being transgender, and fewer depressive symptoms among transgender adolescents, underscoring the protective effect of family acceptance on mental health.^[14]

Family support fosters a sense of belonging and validation, which is essential for building resilience and promoting mental well-being. Parental acceptance is crucial for developing a healthy sense of self and

improving overall well-being among lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) youth, especially in transgender individuals.^[15] Conversely, lack of family support can exacerbate feelings of isolation and dysphoria, leading to poorer mental health outcomes. Family rejection contributes to higher rates of depression, anxiety, and suicidal ideation. Specifically, LGBT youth who experience high levels of family rejection are 8.4 times more likely to report having attempted suicide, 5.9 times more likely to report high levels of depression, and 3.4 times more likely to use illegal drugs compared to their peers who experience low or no family rejection.^[16] Therefore, it is imperative for healthcare providers to encourage and facilitate family involvement in the care of transgender patients.

CONCLUSIONS

This review highlights the complex interplay between transgender medicine and mental health. Endocrine treatments using HT, gender-affirming surgery and strong support are associated with significant improvements in mental health outcomes for transgender individuals. Conversely, lack of treatment and lower socioeconomic status are linked to poorer mental health outcomes. Healthcare professionals must consider these factors when developing and providing care for transgender patients. Future research should focus on addressing barriers to care and exploring additional interventions to support the mental health of transgender individuals.

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